

DESIGNING AN ENGLISH CLUB WEBSITE – A PRACTICAL SOLUTION FOR PROMOTING THE POPULARITY AND EFFICIENCY OF ENGLISH CLUB AT HO CHI MINH CITY UNIVERSITY OF TRANSPORT

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ABSTRACT

Teaching English as a language is actually a process that enables students to develop language skills in communication activities, therefore, it is really necessary to have a combination of academic programs with the outside class curriculum to maximize the opportunity to study, practice, supplement the knowledge of this language. The English Club is a promising environment to hold such types of outside activities for English learners. However, surveys of the English club's performance show that the role and impact of the English club on teaching and learning at the University are not high at present. The lack of properly operating conditions, together with the lack of educational orientation and a systematic curriculum make the English club not really close, even unknown in a large number of students of the University.

In the search for solutions to these issues, the idea of building a website for the English club has been cooked in the author's heart. After a process of studying, building, running, evaluating and adjusting, the English club website - the final product was created in hopes of bringing a positive change in the role and performance of the English club, thereby contributing to improving the quality of English teaching at the HCMC University of Transport.

Key words: English Club, English- learning website, extra-curriculum.

1 INTRODUCTION

English Club –an entity of people who share the same aptitude, interest and inclination to work and help each other to learn and practice English skills through activities such as seminars, role-plays, discussions, workshops... Most of researches in the world agree upon in the aspect of language learning and teaching is that the more conducive and supportive the learning environment is, the more successful the learner outcome will be, and a lot of researchers have proved that English club can create such type of environment for language learners.

However, according to the data source the author found in some surveys of English club at UT, English club is still unfamiliar and even unknown by a big number of students at the university. The activities of English club have received very little attention and participation from the

students, so English club at UT now, in fact, has not much positive influence on the language learners' acquisition.

The surveys showed that students are reluctant to join English club activities because of some reasons like a long distance to EC venue, their lack of confidence in their English skills to meet other students in person for discussion or seminars....Some students don't have any information of English club's activities and don't know how to register to become the club members.

“How can English club be more popular to the UT students?”

“By which way can we make English club more interesting and closer to the UT students?”

“How can we make English club become a conducive, supportive and academic environment to English learners at UT?”

Those questions have possessed the author's mind for a long time, and the idea of designing an English club website came out as one of the practical solutions.

This idea has become a strong and convincible thought when the author found a lot of the same views on the importance of websites in teaching and learning language from many scholars in the world.

2 REVIEW OF LITERATURE

There are many positive perspectives among the researchers all over the world towards the website influence on language learners. Min Liu (2008) supposed that websites can be a useful source in promoting English learning. They provide highly practical types of exercises that motivate students and ensure that they facilitate the understanding of English.

Gu (2002), Kung & Chuo (2002), Lin (2003) demonstrated in their studies that the use of web-based activities has a positive effect on the development of communication skills and writing of students. Hoecherl-A den (2000), Osuna&Meskill (1998) agreed that web-enhanced activities promote students 'development of deep cultural understanding while enhancing language proficiency and creativity. Many learning activities motivate learners to participate more (Hoecherl-Aden 2000)(Plass 1998).

The design of a good website for learning language is discussed among the scholars.

According to Plass (1998), website design should support cognitive processes that involve developing language skills and practical knowledge for language learners. Phyo (2003) suggested that a good design should create a positive experience for the users and could lead to desired cognitive outcomes. Krug (2005) demonstrated that understanding the needs and interests of users can help create websites that meet their expectations and goals. Min Lui (2008) states that website design should address three essential components of information, interface and interaction. He also asked the web designers to consider the following five questions before carrying on design:

1. Who is the website designed for, which skills are focused on training, what topics, what kind of exercise?
2. Are pages easy to follow in terms of page length, layout, and density of content, colors and fonts?
3. How many clicks do web users need to get to exactly what they care about, and is getting back to the main page easy?
4. What knowledge or level of competence do the English users need to have to understand the content on the menu bar, or the sorting columns?
5. Do activities or tasks on the website support this second language acquisition? Are the objectives of the activities and the way to achieve these goals clearly expressed?

Therefore, English-learning websites can be seen as a dispensable teaching tool in modern education. The designer of website should know well the needs and interests of the users to satisfy their expectations because that's the key factor deciding the success of a website.

With the fundamental knowledge and basis of designing a language website, the author carried on the vital steps to build up a website for UT English Club.

3 THE PROCESS OF DESIGNING ENGLISH CLUB WEBSITE

3.1 Identifying Objectives of EC website

From the Krug's point of view, the website designer needs to set the short-term and long-term goals for website clearly before doing the other steps. And with the main aim towards promoting English Club's popularity and efficiency at UT, English Club website objectives should be as follows:

Be a communication channel, bringing pictures and activities of the English club closer to the majority of students at UT

Create a friendly, academic English learning environment for all students at School.

Orient students in finding the best strategies for learning and passing the final exam as well as the international English exams such as TOEIC, IELTS...

Establish a free and reliable forum for students to share their views on hot issues in life.

Provide useful material resources for learning English.

Be an active channel to build up a good bond between students and students, students and faculty.

3.2 Identifying the subject of the website

The website is targeted at a wide range of students, from different levels of English, from beginner to intermediate level of English at UT.

3.3 Sketching out information or activities provide on the website.

To match with the decisive factors in designing a successful website to language learners

mentioned in the research of Plass (1998), Phyo(2003), Krug(2005), Min Lui (2008), the author took a deep consideration in the information sections on website. The information should be both interesting and useful to support the learners' cognitive process and attain the specific objectives set for UT English club website.

3.3.1 Song review

According to Schoepp (2001), the songs provide enjoyment and develop language skills. Songs also present opportunities for developing automaticity –a component of language fluency. Some songs are excellent examples of colloquial English that is the language of informal conversation. ApinHidayat (2013) proved that songs not only help the teacher to teach listening but also provide an interesting way for the students to achieve the learning goals.

So, "Song review" section is the first choice displayed on web. Each month, there will be an English song introduced, commented on the web. A video clip created by the members of the club introduces the context of the song, the information related to singers, musicians, outstanding achievements of the song. Also in this clip the main points on vocabulary, grammar, pronunciation in the song are also analyzed and shared.

Other students were asked to re-present the song or share their memories and memories with the song in English.

3.3.2 Movie review

Statistics reveals that the adults on average watch 25 minutes of film per day and according to Khabeishvilli (2014), in teaching English as a second language, films help trigger discussions, set up writing tasks and can be used to practice listening skills, learn vocabulary or get students used to hearing how native speakers “really” communicate.

Thus, it is necessary to add “Movie review” to the website information in order to assist in the formation and reinforcement of English language skills.

Each month, there will be a popular movie (in English) suggested on the web. A clip by the members of the club introduces the scene of the film's birth and teaches the main points of vocabulary, grammar, and pronunciation that appear in the film.

Other students were asked to watch the film and answered some questions about the film.

3.3.3 Talkzone

Talkzone is a content area aimed at developing students' speaking skills and for students with pre-intermediate level in English.

In this field, students will record video projects on a topic they care about such as school, friends, or social, economic and cultural issues.

Talkzone promises to provide students with a forum for expressing personal views about life and the place for students' demonstrating their fluency in English.

Students who have a high qualified video project in terms of content and image quality will receive an incentive gift, or a plus point in the final mark.

3.3.4 Idioms / phrases

Cambridge Idiom (2010: VI) states that learners' language skills will increase rapidly if learners understand and use expressions confidently and accurately. Fernando (1996, p.234) supposed "no translator or language teacher can afford to ignore idioms or idiomaticity as a natural use of the target language is an aim".

Therefore, the video clips teaching idioms by the native teachers on YouTube are carefully selected to post on website. The users are asked to watch the video clip and do some clip-related exercises such as matching the meaning, making a new conversation with idioms... to test their understanding and ability in applying what they have learned in each video clip into the real conversation.

3.3.5 Pronunciation challenges

In this section, every month English teachers will present a challenge in pronunciation for students through a short video. These challenges are the key to pronunciation principles such as articulators in the vocal tract, vowels and consonants, minimal pairs, stress, intonation.

Students will leave comments to interact with the teacher and gradually solve the challenge.

Students with the best and fastest answers will appear in the next video to provide a full explanation for the old challenge and set up another challenge for the coming week.

3.3.6 Tutorial center

This is a hopeful section to provide the help needed for students to study.

This section is divided into 3 parts:

Questions and Answers

This section is like a forum where students can ask any questions relating to their English study, or about English club.

Tutoring Services

A list of excellent students in English courses, and means to contact them such as email address, Facebook, phone... is shared publicly. Thanks to that, other students who want to find a friend or tutor to study with can contact them but may incur a small fee for this service.

TOEIC actual tests

With the goal of helping students become familiar with TOEIC test forms, supplementing their basic knowledge of vocabulary, grammar, reading and listening skills through 2-toeic skill tests, the "TOEIC actual test" will help website users have the opportunity to take the TOEIC test to know the current level.

To create the test on the website, the team connected to the website: <https://courses.ut.edu.vn/> to build the electronic test suite. This will also help introduce viewers to this very new online study school website.

3.3.7 E-lab

This section provides students with as many useful English learning materials as possible.

Students can find English-learning materials in the following categories: Textbooks, TOIEC, IELTS, Other references

3.3.8 About us / Gallery / News and events / Contact us.

These arrays are displayed separately on the menu bar, but share a common goal that is to give a good insight of English club at UT.

About us - A general introduction to the English club, history of birth, mode of operation and achievements. In addition, the content and operation of the website are also presented in this section.

Gallery - This is the section that shows regular activities of the club.

News and events - is an array of news or club events that will allow members to schedule their time to join in.

Contact - This section provides ways to contact the club.

3.4 Sketching out website interface.

The interface design process is quite complicated, and it relates to the process of designing the appearance such as color, font, font size, visual, icons... and manipulation such as search functions, links to homepage, breadcrumbs to the site. The IT technicians were invited to carry on designing the interface and interaction sections of website.

3.5 Sketching out website interaction section.

With the goal of creating an interactive learning environment, the design team takes full advantage of today's highly popular social networking applications for embedding in Web sites to stimulate maximizing the engagement between students and students, students and teachers. The software applications that are attached to the website include:

1. YouTube: Code embed audio, video, channel from Club.
2. Google Drive (Audio, Video, and Image): Create an archive of audio, video, image -> archives, online sharing, anti-ads, or similar affiliate links.
3. Google Analytics: Embedded code helps keep track of how many posts you have, so we have an overview of which categories visitors are most likely to navigate to, and to develop appropriate content.

4. Google +, Facebook: Code share, comment on the website, and authenticate user accounts through social channels.

Code embedded phone number, Skype, Zale, Vibe.

6. Chat online: Submit questions directly to Club, email to reply.

7. FAQ: is a channel for answering questions.

4 THE EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVITY OF THE ENGLISH CLUB WEBSITE

Instruments and participants

After completing the designing process, the author carried on the evaluation of the website properties and usefulness with a questionnaire for 350 participants from 10 classes at UT.

The sample of study is quite diverse in terms of English proficiency, including 5 English classes 1 (Elementary level), 3 English B12 classes (pre-intermediate level) , 2 classes of construction economics 1 (intermediate level).

An English-Vietnamese bilingual survey questionnaire consisting of 11 questions was designed, printed and sent to 10 classrooms, issuing a total of 350 copies, collecting 350 copies.

The content of the survey is as follows:

Questions 1-8: assess students' satisfaction for websites related to interface design, quality of content, activity and learning experience on the website.

Question 9: Evaluate the usefulness of the website for improving skills in English.

Question 10-11: Evaluate the possibility the users re-access the website after the first use.

Findings and analysis

With the help of faculty members in the foreign language department, 350 surveys were distributed and collected 350 copies from 10 surveyed classes. Based on the questionnaires collected, the research team began conducting data collection, analysis and evaluation.

Graph 1 shows the corresponding survey results of the 8 questions from 1-8 to assess student satisfaction of the website. The questions of satisfaction are classified according to Likert scale, "Unsatisfied" represents 1-2, "Normal" represents 3, and "Satisfied" represents level 4-5, with a scale of 1 "very not satisfied" to 5 "very satisfied".

From the information shown in graph 1, we can see that the satisfaction level of the website is quite good, mostly 65% or more, only the instruction for activities is at average satisfaction (60%).

Three key elements of the website including content quality, interface style, and learning experience are all at the high satisfaction (from above 80%). The level of satisfaction with easy-to-find and return home content is 100%.

Graph 1: The level of satisfaction on the website properties

Question 9 of the survey was also designed on the Likert scale, with a 5-level scale of usefulness for the student in the skill development and additional knowledge in the subject. English from level 1 "not useful at all" to level 5 "very useful"

To facilitate the presentation of the data on the board, levels 1-2 are generally conventionally "not useful," level 3 is "normal" and levels 4-5 are conventionally "very useful. "

Graph 2: The level of usefulness of the website for improving English skills and knowledge

The chart shows that website sections are very helpful in providing good drills related to listening skills (81%), reading (81%), grammar (91%), writing (78%) and knowledge related to culture

(70%). However, participants considered that speaking skill drills in the sections are insufficient to help them improve their speaking skill (just 55% very useful).

Questions 10 and 11 are concerned about the possibility that students who participated in the survey will be back to access and study on the website, and also the possibility that students will introduce the site to their acquaintances.

Statistics show that 99.9% of students agree to return to the website, 76% of students said they would recommend it to their friends.

5 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

From the findings above it can be said that English club website design is relatively highly appreciated and welcomed by participants. The properties and English skills displayed on the website are concluded to significantly meet the users' needs and interests. However, in reality, the website operation and management are a hard job for the admin who may have to share time with the teaching career or studying. Thus, there are some necessary recommendations that need to be done:

For the Foreign language department

It is necessary to set up an admin team who consists of both teacher advisors and English member students so that it can reduce the balance on any chief admin. The admin team would be recommended to combine the on-web activities with the monthly offline activities to make a significant influence on as many students as possible. Moreover, the participation in the online and offline activities of English club website should be scored and then take account 10% in the students' final mark in English courses. This will encourage students to join more English extra activities and consequently improve more their English skills.

For the University executive board

In order to create the video clip with high quality in image, audio and special effects, the School should have a mini studio equipped with a series of modern technologies such as Full-HD cameras, wireless micros, and a high –quality lighting system.

Besides, the university executive board should take a consideration in promulgating a reward policy in order to encourage the teacher advisors and EC's members to contribute their time and ardor to English club on a long term basis.

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Appendix 1: (Questionnaire)

Site feedback Questionnaire

This questionnaire is for understanding how you feel about the English club website. Please rate the site by circling the appropriate number.

	Very unsatisfied		Neutral	Very satisfied	
1.Ease of finding information/ activities	1	2	3	4	5
2. Quality of information/ activities	1	2	3	4	5
3. Appearance of site, including colors and graphics	1	2	3	4	5
4. Speed of page displaying	1	2	3	4	5
5. Fun, entertainment value	1	2	3	4	5
6.Overral learning experience	1	2	3	4	5
7. Ease of understanding the instruction for activities	1	2	3	4	5
8. Ease of moving around the site without getting lost	1	2	3	4	5

9. Mark how useful this site is for improving the English skill you practiced.

	Check the skills that you practiced	Useless		Neutral	Very useful	
Speaking		1	2	3	4	5
Listening		1	2	3	4	5
Reading		1	2	3	4	5
Writing		1	2	3	4	5
Grammar		1	2	3	4	5
Culture		1	2	3	4	5

10. Are you likely to return to this site on your own?

Yes

No

Explain why you are or are not likely to return to this site?

.....
.....

11. Would you recommend using this site to your friends who are learning English at our university?

No way -2 -1 0 1 2 I'll definitely recommend this site

Appendix 2

Link website : <http://englishclub.ut.edu.vn/>